

An X-Ray Analysis of the Radio Loud Quasar 3C 270.1

Moiya McTier, Belinda Wilkes

Abstract

Originally intended for use in quantifying the orientation dependence of AGN (Active Galactic Nucleus) observations, the radio-loud quasar 3C 270.1 shows extended structure possibly related to a high-redshift ($z=1.532$) galaxy cluster. We have analyzed a 97 ks observation taken with the *Chandra* ACIS-S instrument to search for the extended X-Ray emission that was first observed in the optical with a surplus of red galaxies (Haas et al, 2009). Excluding the radio-related X-Rays found in the northern and southern lobes, we detect 50.2 ± 20.8 counts in a $6''$ to $19''$ annulus centered on the quasar. Using PIMMS, we estimated a flux of $2.7e-15$ erg/s, which, at this redshift, corresponds to a luminosity of $2e43$ erg/s.

Introduction

Quasars (Quasi-stellar radio sources) are a class of AGN that are brighter and more energetic than all of the stars in a typical galaxy combined. One of the difficulties with studying quasars is the dependence of our observations on their orientation with respect to us. To try to quantify this dependence, Wilkes and her colleagues selected a non-biased sample from the 3rd Cambridge Catalogue of Radio Sources, including 3C 270.1, and analyzed them in the X-Ray with *Chandra* in 2008. Extended emission was seen around 3C 270.1, which prompted a request for deeper observations, which were taken in 2012.

Quasars are typically found in dense regions of the universe because the black holes that form them need large stores of matter to do so. Since galaxy clusters are overly-dense regions in the universe, quasars make good beacons for finding galaxy clusters. 3C 270.1 is a particularly interesting beacon because a redshift of $z=1.5$ corresponds to a universal age of about 4 Gyr, which is too young for the universe to have allowed fully-formed galaxy clusters to develop. Therefore, even though this isn't a particularly high redshift for a quasar, it is very high for a galaxy cluster.

A spectral analysis of the quasar provides a spectrum from which to model the quasar's PSF (Point Spread Function). Spectral analysis is possible because X-Ray observations include accounts of the energy, time of arrival, and location of each incoming photon. X-Ray spectra typically have a power-law form

$$F_{\nu} \sim \nu^{-\alpha}$$

where the slope, α , is specified in terms of the photon index, $\Gamma=1+\alpha$. A comparison of the radial profiles of 3C 270.1 and its model PSF will be used to extract the number of counts in the quasar's extended structure, believed to be associated with the surrounding galaxy cluster.

An analysis of the 2008 *Chandra* data on 3C 270.1 revealed a slope with $\Gamma=1.64 \pm 0.08$, a dimmer and softer result than what we see with the 2012 data. They estimated a luminosity of about $2e44$ erg/s for the extended emission that may be associated with a surrounding galaxy cluster.

Data

Chandra observations of 3C 270.1, a radio-loud quasar catalogued in the Third Cambridge Radio Catalogue, were taken in 2008 with a 10 ks exposure time (Wilkes et al, 2012). Deeper observations of the quasar were proposed to analyze the surrounding galaxy cluster, and the data were taken on March 04, 2012 (See Table 1). The second observations were taken with the *Chandra* ACIS-S instrument with an exposure time of 96.59 ks, allowing for a much deeper image than the first exposure time of 9.67 ks.

The radio data were observed with the A configuration of the EVLA (Expanded Very Large Array) on October 14, 2012. They were taken in the S band (2.7 GHz) with a 6-hour exposure and reduced by our collaborator, Mark Birkinshaw, at the University of Bristol, UK. The new data show new low-surface-brightness to the south of the bend in the northern jet (see Figure 2), but not north of that, as was seen in the earlier data.

Instrument	Obs ID	Date Taken	Exposure Time
<i>Chandra</i>	9255	Feb. 16, 2008	9.67 ks
<i>Chandra</i>	13906	March 4, 2012	96.59 ks
EVLA	--	Oct. 14, 2012	6 hrs

Table 1: Details of the Radio and X-Ray observations

Data Analysis

Spectral Fit of the Quasar Core

To analyze the emission from the quasar, we made a spectral fit (see Figure 2). We used ds9 to define the quasar region and a background region (See Figure 1). After subtracting the background from the source, we used CIAO (<http://cxc.harvard.edu/ciao/>) — a *Chandra* analysis software package — to extract the counts for the core and Sherpa (<http://cxc.harvard.edu/sherpa/>) — a sub-environment of CIAO used in modeling and fitting—to fit the power-law spectrum. The fit doesn't look like a power-law (see Figure 2) because Sherpa's plotting software takes the instruments response into account.

A trial analysis of 3C 270.1 was done without taking pileup into account. Pileup is an instrumental feature inherent to *Chandra* that allows counts to build up for high-count sources. Two photons get counted as one at the sum of their energies, which, for bright sources, appears at the peak of the point spread function, where most of the counts fall. 3C 270.1 is bright enough that about 10% of the counts should be piled up in the center, which could flatten the fit to the quasar's spectrum and decrease the number of counts we find in our analysis.

To determine how much of an effect the pileup had on the initial analysis, we fit power-laws to the spectra of the source both including and excluding the four central pixels that would have been affected by pileup. We also fit a power-law to the spectrum of the central pixels by themselves. After comparing the slope of the quasar's spectral fit and its slope without considering the counts from the central pixel (see Table 2) and seeing that they are consistent well within 2 sigma, we determined that the pileup didn't have a significant effect on any subsequent data analysis. All subsequent analyses will be done with the quasar's full spectral fit.

When making the spectral fits, we assumed an obscuring Galactic hydrogen column density of $N_{\text{H}}=1.29 \times 10^{20}$ atoms/cm³ according to the power-law spectral fit described in Wilkes, et al, 2012.

Figure 1: *Chandra* X-Ray image showing the quasar core (inner circle, radius=3'') and the background region (inner radius=5.75'', outer radius=11.5'')

Figure 2: Spectral fit to the quasar core with counts in black, the fit in red, and residuals in the bottom panel

X-Ray Regions

We identified three X-Ray regions associated with the radio (see Figure 3) by superimposing the radio contours onto the X-Ray data. This X-Ray emission is due to inverse Compton scattering from lower-energy photons and is unrelated to the thermal emission from the hot gas in the cluster. The first of the regions is in the quasar's northern jet, ending at the 40° bend in the jet, after which radio emission continues to be seen, but we see no X-Ray emission. The second was the entire southern lobe, and the third was the hotspot of the southern lobe, where the peak of the X-Ray emission is located. We made spectral fits of all three X-Ray regions (see Table 2) using the same background region we used when fitting the quasar (see *Quasar Spectral Fit* section).

Figure 3: Images of the EVLA Radio Data and contours (left) and un-smoothed Chandra X-Ray data showing Radio-Associated X-Ray Regions (right)

Figure 4: Spectral fits to the radio-associated X-Ray regions

Determining Counts from Extended Structure

One way to determine if there is actually a cluster near the quasar is to find how many photons we are receiving from the extended structure seen in the *Chandra* data. We did this by comparing the radial profiles of the quasar and its model PSF.

To create the radial profile of the quasar, we first created a version of the *Chandra* data without any of the radio-related X-Ray emission (see Figure 5)—a result of either synchrotron radiation or inverse compton scattering, neither of which are thermal emission mechanisms, which is what the X-Rays from a galaxy cluster would be. In order to remove the non-thermal X-Ray emission from the data, we must identify and remove the X-Ray regions associated with the radio.

In that no-radio version, we defined radial regions—annuli expanding radially from the quasar at 5-pixel (about 2.5 arcseconds) intervals—starting outside the quasar core (radius=1'') and reaching to a radius of 22''. At this redshift, 1'' corresponds to ≈ 8.2 kpc. The average size of a galaxy cluster is 0.5-1 Mpc (Hansen, et al, 2005), so we went out to about 20% the radius of the average galaxy cluster. Beyond this radius, radial profiles revealed that the signal was dominated by noise, which implies that any cluster which surrounds 3C 270.1 is smaller than average. We defined a separate background region (with an inner radius of 25 arcsec and an outer radius of 30 arcsec from the quasar core) from the one used in the spectral fit for the quasar. Using CIAO again, we extracted the counts from each radial region.

Figure 5: Radio-associated regions excluded in the no-radio version of the data set (left) and radial regions and background used in the radial profile (right)

A high signal-to-noise model PSF was generated from the spectrum of the quasar by Dr. Wilkes using *Chandra*'s ray-tracing software, ChaRT (<http://cxc.harvard.edu/chart/>). Using the same radial regions used for the quasar, but not subtracting a background as none was included

in the PSF model, we extracted the counts from each region. The PSF counts were normalized to the quasar's core (see Figure 6) by summing the counts of the quasar and the PSF out to a radius of 9'' and dividing the counts in the PSF's radial regions by the ratio of the sums.

Once the PSF was normalized to the quasar core, we compared the radial profiles outside the normalized region to search for significant extended emission in the observed data. The number of excess extended source counts which may be associated with a cluster can be found by separately summing up the counts for the AGN and PSF between the edge of the quasar core and 24'' (after which the signal becomes dominated by noise; see Figure 6) and taking the difference between the two sums.

Figure 6: Radial Profiles of the quasar (red) and its model PSF (blue) and a zoomed-in image (bottom)

Results

After taking the difference of the counts from the quasar and its model PSF, we found that we were receiving 50.2 ± 20.8 counts (a marginal detection) from the extended structure, starting at about $5''$ from the quasar core and extending to $20''$. This corresponds to a count rate of 0.0005 ± 0.0003 ct/s.

Region Name	Net Counts 0.3-8 keV	Hardness Ratio ^a	Slope Γ	Flux Density keV ^b	Flux 0.3-8 keV ^c	Flux 0.3-2 keV ^c	Flux 2-8 keV ^c
Quasar Core	8284	-0.33	1.42 ± 0.02	1.75	8.70	2.95	5.77
Quasar w/o Central Pixel	5599	-0.32	1.37 ± 0.03	1.30	6.79	2.18	4.62
N Jet Bend	110	-0.34	1.83 ± 0.3	0.022	0.080	0.039	0.041
S Jet	132	-0.56	1.85 ± 0.22	0.029	0.104	0.052	0.052
S hotspot	80	-0.52	1.9 ± 0.3	0.018	0.064	0.032	0.032

Table 2: X-Ray Counts and Derived Parameters

^a $HR=(H-S)/(H+S)$; (H(2-8keV)) and (S(0.3-2keV))

^b In units of $10^{-13} \text{ erg cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ keV}^{-1}$

^c In units of $10^{-13} \text{ erg cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$

Discussion and Conclusions

Using PIMMS (Portable, Interactive Multi-Mission Simulator), and assuming a temperature of 4 keV, we converted the count rate for the extended emission to a flux of 2.7×10^{-15} erg/s, which, at a redshift of $z=1.532$, corresponds to an estimated luminosity of 4.1×10^{43} erg/s. This is about a factor of 3 lower than the luminosity determined using the 2008 data, which revealed 22.8 ± 5.8 counts in 10% of the exposure time for a count rate of 0.0024 ± 0.0006 ct/s.

New EVLA data (see Figure 3) revealed extended radio emission southeast of the northern radio lobe that was not seen in the original radio data which was used to define the radio-related X-Ray regions in the earlier analysis of 3C 270.1 (Wilkes, et al, 2012). We extracted 55 ± 20 (depending on how we define the region) counts from this region. This means that roughly half of the 22.8 counts determined to be associated with the extended structure in Wilkes, et al, 2012 are actually associated with the radio. With this correction, the luminosity estimated with the 2012 *Chandra* data is only a factor of two off from that estimated using the 2008 data. This luminosity is still low (by a factor of about 10) for an assumed temperature of 4 keV based on an L-T relation derived in Pratt, et al, 2009.

Because both the 2008 and 2012 *Chandra* datasets resulted in a marginal detection of a galaxy cluster surrounding 3C 270.1, a more accurate value for the counts from the extended emission could be found using a detailed spectral fit to constrain the temperature. That is the next step in the project, and will be used to further explain the difference in the results from the 2008 and 2012 *Chandra* data.

References

- Haas, Martin, et al. "Clustering of Red Galaxies Around the $z = 1.53$ Quasar 3C 270.1." *The Astrophysical Journal*, 2009.
- Hansen, Sarah, et al. "Measurement of Galaxy Cluster Sizes, Radial Profiles, and Luminosity Functions from SDSS Photometric Data." *The Astrophysical Journal*, 2005.
- Peterson, B. M. *An Introduction to Active Galactic Nuclei*. Cambridge: Cambridge UP, 2004. Print.
- Pratt, G. W., Croston, J. H., Arnaud, M., & Bohringer, H. 2009, " *A&A*, 498, 361
- Wilkes, Belinda J., et al. "X-Ray Observations Of The Redshift 1.53 Radio-Loud Quasar 3C 270.1." *The Astrophysical Journal* 745.1 (2012): 84. Web.